

Organisation **University of Algarve**
Department **Centre of Marine and Environmental Research**

NAUTILOS

Deliverable 11.4

Environmental Impact
Assessment - final

Date: 28-07-2024

Doc. Version: V5.0

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14283263

Document Control Information

Settings	Value
Deliverable Title	NAUTILOS Environmental Impact Assessment - final
Work Package Title	Exploitation and Impact
Deliverable number	11.4
Description	An EIA for an assessment of the environmental impacts of the development and demonstration activities within NAUTILOS and their cumulative effects. Final version
Lead Beneficiary	CIMA - UAIG
Lead Authors	Andre Costa Neves & Maria João Bebianno (UAIG)
Contributors	Catarina Lemos (CEiiA)
Submitted by	Andre Costa Neves (UAIG)
Doc. Version (Revision number)	Version 3.0
Sensitivity (Security):	Basic
Date:	23/07/2024

Document Approver(s) and Reviewer(s):

NOTE: All Approvers are required. Records of each approver must be maintained. All Reviewers in the list are considered required unless explicitly listed as Optional.

Name	Role	Action	Date
Gabriele Pieri	Review Team 1	Approved high-level skeleton	26/06/2024
Natali Dimitrova	Review Team 1	Approve	04/07/2024
Michela Martinelli	Review Team 2	Review	26/06/2024
Manolis Ntoumas	Review Team 2	Review	28/06/2024
Christophe Guinet	Review Team 2	Review	05/07/2024
Damien Malarde	Review Team 2	Review	12/07/2024
Jorge Fontes	Review Team 2	Review	12/07/2024
Paula Salge	Review Team 2	Review	17/07/2024

Christos Tsabaris	Review Team 2	Review	22/07/2024
Andy Smerdon	Review Team 2	Review	25/07/2024

Document history:

The Document Author is authorized to make the following types of changes to the document without requiring that the document be re-approved:

- Editorial, formatting, and spelling
- Clarification

To request a change to this document, contact the Document Author or Owner.

Changes to this document are summarized in the following table in reverse chronological order (latest version first).

Revision	Date	Created by	Short Description of Changes
V5.0	23/07/2024	Andre Costa Neves	Final version
V4.0	17/07/2024	Andre Costa Neves	Reviewed version
V3.0	14/06/2024	Andre Costa Neves	First submitted version
V2.0	22/04/2024	Andre Costa Neves	Final draft sent for internal review
V1.0	10/03/2024	Andre Costa Neves	Initial draft

Configuration Management: Document Location

The latest version of this controlled document is stored in <location>.

Nature of the deliverable		
R	Report	X
DEC	Websites, patents, filing, etc.	
DEM	Demonstrator	
O	Other	

Dissemination level		
PU	Public	X
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This report forms part of the deliverables from the NAUTILOS project which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000825. The Community is not responsible for any use that might be made of the content of this publication.

NAUTILOS - New Approach to Underwater Technologies for Innovative, Low-cost Ocean observation is an H2020 project funded under the Future of Seas and Oceans Flagship Initiative, coordinated by the National Research Council of Italy (CNR, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche). It brings together a group of 21 entities from 11 European countries with multidisciplinary expertise ranging from ocean instrumentation development and integration, ocean sensing and sampling instrumentation, data processing, modelling and control, operational oceanography and biology and ecosystems and biogeochemistry such, water and climate change science, technological marine applications and research infrastructures.

NAUTILOS will fill-in marine observation and modelling gaps for chemical, biological and deep ocean physics variables through the development of a new generation of cost-effective sensors and samplers, the integration of the aforementioned technologies within observing platforms and their deployment in large-scale demonstrations in European seas. The fundamental aim of the project will be to complement and expand current European observation tools and services, to obtain a collection of data at a much higher spatial resolution, temporal regularity and length than currently available at the European scale, and to further enable and democratise the monitoring of the marine environment to both traditional and non-traditional data users.

NAUTILOS is one of two projects included in the EU's efforts to support of the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy by supporting the demonstration of new and innovative technologies to measure the Essential Ocean Variables (EOV).

More information on the project can be found at: <https://nautilus-h2020.eu/>

COPYRIGHT

© NAUTILOS Consortium. Copies of this publication – also of extracts thereof – may only be made with reference to the publisher.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1.	ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	4
2.	COPYRIGHT	4
3.	TABLE OF CONTENTS	5
5.	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
6.	LIST OF FIGURES	8
7.	LIST OF TABLES	8
8.	LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS	8
I.	FOREWORD	10
II.	INTRODUCTION	10
1.	Description of the project	10
2.	Legislation	10
3.	Objectives.....	10
4.	Justification	11
5.	Location of the project.....	11
III.	METHODOLOGY	11
1.	Screening.....	12
2.	Scoping.....	14
3.	Review of the Environment Impact Statement.....	14
IV.	MAIN IMPACTS, MITIGATION, PREVENTION AND MANAGEMENT OF POTENTIAL ADVERSE EFFECTS	15
9.	DEVELOPMENT OF MARINE TECHNOLOGY	15
9.1.	Materials.....	15
9.2.	Disposal alternatives.....	16
9.3.	Batteries.....	17
9.4.	Antifouling	17
9.5.	Non-Technical Summary.....	18
10.	DEMONSTRATIONS	19
10.1.	Loss of equipment.....	20
10.2.	Ship Operations.....	20
10.3.	Noise pollution	21
10.4.	Chemical Impacts.....	21
10.5.	Autonomous Vehicles /Platforms	22

10.6.	ARGO Floats	23
11.	IMPACTS AND MITIGATION MEASURES FROM SPECIFIC SENSORS AND ASSOCIATED DEPLOYMENTS	23
11.1.	Sensors and samplers	23
11.1.1.	Fluorometric Sensors/dissolved oxygen	25
11.1.2.	Dissolved Oxygen and Fluorescence Sensors.....	25
11.1.3.	Downward-looking multi/hyperspectral and laser induced fluorescence sensors and cameras.....	26
11.1.4.	Passive broadband acoustic recording sensor for noise monitoring / Passive acoustic event recorder / Active Acoustic Profiling Sensor	27
11.1.5.	Sampler for phytoplankton and other suspended matter.....	28
11.1.6.	Carbonate system/ocean acidification sensors	28
11.1.7.	Silicate Electrochemical Sensor.....	29
11.1.8.	Submersible Nano- and Microplastics Sampler - Submersible Sampler for Nanoplastics and Microplastics (SCT)	29
11.1.9.	Low-cost Microplastic sensors based on selective Nile Red staining and fluorescence detection	30
11.1.10.	Deep Ocean CTD	31
11.1.11.	Deep ocean low-level radioactivity sensor	31
11.1.12.	Animal-borne sensor (sharks and rays).....	32
11.1.13.	Animal-borne tag (elephant seals).....	35
11.2.	Deployments	37
11.2.1.	Demonstrations on Fisheries and Aquaculture Observing Systems.....	37
11.2.2.	Demonstration on platforms of opportunity	38
11.2.3.	Demonstrations on Augmented Observing Systems	38
11.2.4.	Demonstration on ARGO platform	38
11.2.5.	Animal-borne instruments	39
V.	FINAL CONSIDERATIONS	39
VI.	APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS	40

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable is the final report from the Task 11.3, which consisted in a robust Environmental Impact Assessment from the NAUTILOS activities. Therefore, it has been carried out, through the course of the project, an extensive evaluation of the possible impacts caused by the NAUTILOS activities. The results and the description of the process of evaluating is reported in detail in this deliverable.

The impact assessment was conducted following rigorously the guidelines from the European Directive of assessment of the effects of certain public and private projects on the environment (DIRECTIVE 2011/92/EU). Briefly, it described the characteristics of the project, the methodology adopted for the evaluation, the possible impacts expected during the development phase, operation and end of life of these sensors. The possible impacts were also assessed with regard to the development and demonstrations within the scope of the project, with each developed technology and demonstration activity discussed in detail. For each negative impact, mitigation measures were provided, and good environmental practices recommended aiming to minimise the possible negative impacts.

This deliverable (D11.4) in conjunction with the Deliverable 11.6 consists of a complete and thorough environmental impact assessment. It adopted a standard approach for impact assessment, starting by the screening followed by the scoping phase, systematic review of these phases, with periodic consultation of the stakeholders, providing recommendations for the Consortium and collecting information throughout the project.

The possible impacts identified were of small magnitude, the sensors, samplers, tags and platforms developed within this project are cutting-edge technology with remarkably low impact, based on passive and non-destructive methods. The sensors can be reused multiple times, and the recovery systems are well developed and tested. It is safe to say that these sensors are among the ones with the lowest level of negative environmental impact in the market within their category. Nevertheless, in this report it is provided an extensive list of good practices and mitigation measures that are being adopted to considerably minimise the magnitude and prevalence of the impacts identified.

The assessment of the environmental impact is a recommended practice in any project, with the aim to identify, reduce and communicate possible negative impacts. By discussing the expected impacts of a project, all parties benefit, enabling decision makers to make more informed, fact-based choices. When considering the positive impacts of the NAUTILOS project, it is evident that the quantity and quality of data generated are far more beneficial for environmental conservation than any negative impacts.

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Consecutive stages of the process to conduct an Environmental Impact Assessment.	12
Figure 2: The “crossed out bin” logo of the WEEE Directive 2012/19/EU	17
Figure 3: Design of the non-technical summary for the environmental impact assessment for marine technologies.	19
Figure 4: Tagging procedure for blue shark and sicklefin devil ray with a harness.....	33
Figure 5: Tagging procedure for sixgill sharks, placing them into a natural tonic immobility position.	34
Figure 6: An elephant seal successfully instrumented.	37

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Locations of the demonstration phase.	11
Table 2: Model questionnaire sent to each partner to collect information about the screening process.....	13
Table 3: Matrix of impacts. The list of sensors, the identified impacts and respective magnitude.	24
Table 4: Potential impacts of animal-borne sensors.	33

LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
ARGOS	Advanced Research and Global Observation Satellite
CTD	conductivity, temperature, and depth
EOVs	Essential Ocean Variables
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
MPA	Marine Protected Area

NAUTILOS	New Approach to Underwater Technologies for Innovative, Low-cost Ocean Observation
UNCLOS	United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea
VHF	Very High Frequency
Hz	Hertz (cycles per second)

I. FOREWORD

Task 11.3 from the project NAUTILOS predicted in the Consortium Agreement requires the University of Algarve to “conduct a robust Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) to assess and minimise significant ecological impacts of NAUTILOS activities”. This task aims to integrate a sustainable approach alongside all project activities avoiding potentially adverse environmental impacts. The development of this task is reported through both an initial version of the impact assessment and an updated complete version of the EIA, respectively Deliverable 11.6 and 11.4.

This document consists of the Deliverable 11.4 which compiles and concludes all the activities regarding the environmental impact assessment. The initial version of the EIA (D11.6) provided recommendations and a preliminary assessment of the activities within the scope of the project. It was submitted in September 2022 (month 24) with the aim to allow the partners to make changes and redesign the activities to indeed reduce the negative impact of the project. This current version, close to the end of the project, will report the impact assessment process and it represents the final version of the EIA.

Since much information was already provided in the initial version (D11.6) to allow the redesign and changes of the activities at earlier stages of the project, this document will provide complementary information to the first assessment. Therefore, both deliverables represent the robust environmental impact assessment required by the Task 11.3.

In addition, since it was given a clear orientation that repetition should be avoided among deliverables, the partner responsible for the EIA understood that a complete and correct impact assessment document must have a set of information (which some was already given). Therefore, it was decided that the best way to present the EIA in complete and comprehensible manner, and avoiding repetition, would be giving references to the previous deliverables’ sections. Some sections are updated with new information collected during the second phase of the impact assessment; thus, only the updated information will be included in this deliverable with the respective reference to the other deliverables.

II. INTRODUCTION

1. DESCRIPTION OF THE PROJECT

This section is described in Deliverable 11.6 section 1.1.

2. LEGISLATION

This section is described in Deliverable 11.6 section 1.2.

3. OBJECTIVES

Since this project developed, integrated and demonstrated cutting-edge technologies to sense the marine environment, the objective of this EIA is (1) to identify the significant possible environmental impacts, (2) to develop mitigation measures to reduce the magnitude of these predicted impacts, and (3) to present recommendations to the Consortium. This current deliverable represents a report on the EIA process that was carried out during the project.

4. JUSTIFICATION

This section is described in Deliverable 11.6 section 2.2.

5. LOCATION OF THE PROJECT

In this project, the activities from the development and demonstration phases are carried out by the partners belonging to the NAUTILOS Consortium located in eleven different European countries. The magnitude of the impacts originated from NAUTILOS activities is not expected to transcend local boundaries. For this reason, emphasis will be given to the areas where the sensors are being demonstrated. They will be described in more detail in the following sections, a list of the sites can be found in Table 1.

Table 1: Locations of the demonstration phase.

Demonstration	Location
Fisheries Observing Systems	Adriatic Sea; Bay of Biscay; Greece; Italy and Portugal
Aquaculture Observing Systems	Coastal Norway and Greece
Marine Mammals Monitoring Systems	Swedish Sound/Kullaberg/Lysekil waters; Portofino MPA cetaceans' sanctuary
Platforms of Opportunity	Trollfjord; Gulf of Finland; Cretan Sea
Argo Platform	Mediterranean Sea, up to 2000 m
Animal-borne Instruments	Azores islands; Valdes Peninsula

III. METHODOLOGY

By definition, EIA is a systematic process that aims to examine in advance the consequences on the natural environment from the development of an activity. The objective is to prevent possible significant impacts by assessing the activities predicted in a systematic, holistic and

multidisciplinary way (Glasson & Therivel, 2013). The EIA process carried out for the NAUTILOS project followed rigorously the consecutive steps outlined in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Consecutive stages of the process to conduct an Environmental Impact Assessment.

Typically, the fundamental steps in EIA can be summarised as screening the possible impacts, scoping stage, presenting the partial results and review of the impact assessment. Hence, guaranteeing that the environmental considerations are properly considered during the course of the project. Therefore, the environmental impacts from the sensors developed in this project were assessed following the consecutive steps: identification, evaluation, magnitude comparison, prevalence, duration, risk, importance, and possible mitigation (Mongkol, 1982).

1. SCREENING

Introductory part of this section on the Deliverable 11.6 section 2.5. Complemented by the text below.

The screening process was conducted to identify the significant impacts originated from the activities of the NAUTILOS project. Followed by a detailed evaluation, the impacts screened

out are investigated more in detail and classified as significant or not significant. A case-by-case approach was used to evaluate the impact of each sensor produced and the demonstration activity. The screening was conducted following the orientation given in the Annex III mentioned in the paragraph 3 from the article 4 of the Directive 2014/52/EU of the European Parliament and of the European Council of 16 April 2014 on the assessment of the effects of certain public and private projects on the environment. Therefore, a spreadsheet (Table 2) was prepared based on the selection criteria presented in the Annex III of the latter. The information presented in this spreadsheet was the basis of the EIA, giving tangible orientations regarding:

1. the characteristics of project;
2. the location of project;
3. type and characteristics of the potential impacts.

The spreadsheet was sent to each sensors' producer multiple times to provide information for the elaboration of the EIA through the course of the project. After examining the information provided, the respective partners were contacted to clarify the information given and to provide additional information on some particular characteristics of the equipment. The template of the screening questionnaire is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Model questionnaire sent to each partner to collect information about the screening process.

Screening Questionnaire
Location
Location where the equipment will be deployed
Size and design of the equipment
Cumulation with other known existing and/or approved projects
Presence of nature reserves or very sensitive environmental areas nearby
Information about the equipment
Description of the composition and quantity (approximated) of materials
Use of biodegradable materials?
Explanation of the sensor technology used / sampling technique
Type of battery used
Anti-fouling strategy
Photo or schema of the design of the sensor
Emission of residues, pollution, nuisances
Heat
Noise pollution
Radiation
Electricity
Light
Release chemicals substances
Any other significant negative impact?
Possible alternative to these impacts?

Life cycle of the equipment
Deployment
Operation / Demonstration
Recovery-at-sea strategies
Disposal and recycling alternatives
Risk of accidents / failing to recover the equipment
Measures to mitigate in case of loss
Legislation
Do you have to follow national/international legislation to develop the sensor?

Any human activity has the potential to originate anthropogenic impact and the role of the Screening phase is to assess whether this impact is significant, manageable, and acceptable, resulting in a selected number of expected impacts to be investigated in more detail in the scoping phase.

2. SCOPING

Introductory part of this section on the Deliverable 11.6 section 2.7. Complemented by the text below.

The impacts and mitigation measures were compiled and presented during the Consortium Meetings and discussed with the partners for improvement and seeking feedback from experts involved also in the demonstrations. The first version of the EIA (D11.6) initially presented the impacts predicted for the developing phase, providing general recommendations for developers.

A usual approach to summarise and illustrate the array of impacts from a project during the different phases (or different sensors in our case) is through a matrix of impacts. This is very useful to have an overview of all specific phases of the project. A matrix of impacts (Table 3) was built for this purpose, with the significant impacts displayed in the column's titles and each respective sensor and/or activity in the rows, the different colours representing the expected magnitude of the impacts.

3. REVIEW OF THE ENVIRONMENT IMPACT STATEMENT

As a standard practice and conducted in most EIAs, the presentation of the results for a public review is usually when the impact and mitigation measures are analysed by others than the team that produced the impact assessment. The partial results are presented, openly discussed and reviewed for a more realistic decision-making process. Furthermore, this is the stage at which the point of view of all the stakeholders is to be included, making the process of an EIA more democratic and inclusive.

For this purpose, the results obtained during the Screening and Scoping phases were presented during the Consortium Meetings and openly discussed among the partners several times. These presentations aimed to provide recommendations for the partners responsible for the development and demonstration phases of each of the sensors, as well as obtain feedback on other potential impacts and the feasibility of the mitigation measures. After these consultations, a review of the impacts was performed, and the EIA was updated. The mitigation measures were reviewed, and the information collected during these meetings included in the final version of the EIA.

Furthermore, a second round of the screening phase was carried out to collect updated information about the sensors and platforms in a more advanced phase of the project. The approach was similar to the first round of the Screening, in which the questionnaire was sent to the partners to review the information provided. Some partners were also invited for a wrap-up meeting with the EIA group to clarify some possible impacts. To sum up, the presentations of the results during the Consortium Meetings, the second round of the screening and the individual meetings with partners composed the review of the EIA.

IV. MAIN IMPACTS, MITIGATION, PREVENTION AND MANAGEMENT OF POTENTIAL ADVERSE EFFECTS

In this chapter, potential impacts are discussed in section IV.1 (development of marine technology) and section IV.2 (demonstrations). Section IV.3 provides a case-by-case analysis of impacts from sensors (IV.3.1) and deployments (IV.3.2) within the project, relating each sensor/deployment to previously identified impacts. Mitigation measures for each impact are also presented throughout the chapter.

1. DEVELOPMENT OF MARINE TECHNOLOGY

The possible impacts during the development phase are described in this section, with their respective mitigation measures. All the following requirements have been addressed by the technologies developed within the scope of NAUTILOS as much as possible, with the aim of maintaining the initial cost-effective proposal, ensuring proper functioning of the devices, and minimising potential environmental impacts.

1.1. Materials

Introductory part of this section on the Deliverable 11.6 section 4.1. Complemented by the text below.

The impact of material selection is related either to possible harmful substances released when the material is in contact with seawater or with the high-impact activities needed to obtain these elements. Through the course of the impact assessment process, the NAUTILOS

Consortium reported the most relevant materials used in the manufacturing of new sensors and samplers. After a careful analysis of the feedback responses, no highly toxic materials were identified. At the same time, no biodegradable material was reported for the construction of these devices.

Since no device is expected to remain permanently in the marine environment following the demonstrations, the possibility to contaminate the seawater with harmful substances from the sensors would only happen in case of accidental loss. No highly pollutant substances have been reported, the materials that represent more potential to pollute in case of decomposing in the marine environment are trace metals from batteries (addressed in the section IV. 1.4), small amounts of metals (copper, nickel, lead, aluminium, titanium, stainless steel) and various polymers (plastic, rubber, synthetic foam). The evaluation of the demonstration activities and recovery rates indicates that the likelihood of device loss is very low.

During deployment, the materials in contact with seawater are not expected to release a significant amount of toxic compounds to the marine environment due to corrosion, also the housing technologies are designed to prevent contact of some substances with the marine environment. All sensors comply with the recommendations and threshold levels for hazardous substances listed in Directive 2011/65/EU of the European Parliament and Council, dated 8 June 2011 on the restriction of the use of certain hazardous substances in electrical and electronic equipment.

1.2. Disposal alternatives

Introductory part of this section on the Deliverable 11.6 section 4.3. Complemented by the text below.

At the end of these devices' life cycle, parts must be separated into types of materials and properly disposed of, preferably recycling and reuse with the aim to close the industrial loop in a circular economy. The concept of "closing the loop" is when you turn goods that are at the end of their life service into resources for other products, reducing waste and the need for raw materials use. The possibility to repair used devices was ensured by the manufacturer, including in the design features that facilitate the repair and reducing waste.

Following the European Directive for Waste from Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE), all sensors must display the "crossed out bin" symbol (Figure 2), which indicates that the product should not be discarded as unsorted waste but must be sent to separate collection facilities for recovery and recycling.

Figure 2: The “crossed out bin” logo of the WEEE Directive 2012/19/EU

1.3. Batteries

Introductory part of this section on the Deliverable 11.6 section 4.5. Complemented by the text below.

For the batteries that are going to be deployed at high depths, they will be immersed in oil to minimise the risk of pressure build-up within the pressure housing due to leakage or battery fault.

Whenever possible, the sensors are powered by platforms such as oceanographic buoys or ships of opportunity such as ferry boats, reducing the demand for batteries within the sensors. Hence, many sensors opted for platform-provided power. The sensors that will use batteries are the Dissolved Oxygen and Fluorescence Sensors, Acoustic sensors, Submersible Nano- and Microplastics Sampler, Deep Ocean low-level radioactivity sensor and the Animal-borne Instruments. These sensors use lithium-ion or nickel–metal hydride batteries, which are battery types that contain fewer polluting substances in comparison to nickel-cadmium batteries.

1.4. Antifouling

Introductory part of this section on the Deliverable 11.6 section 4.6. Complemented by the text below.

Although fouling can disrupt measurements of marine sensors in less than a week (Delauney et al., 2010), few sensors from NAUTILOS need antifouling technology. For those sensors that require antifouling, a passive protection based on copper is commonly reported. The sensors using antifouling methods are the Fluorometric Sensors/dissolved oxygen, Dissolved Oxygen and Fluorescence Sensors, Deep Ocean low-level radioactivity sensor. Considering longer deployments once these sensors reach the market, the number of sensors that will need antifouling strategies should increase. In this situation, these sensors should adopt widely tested technology to prevent biofouling on instrumentation, in particular fouling protection of the sensing area of the sensor (Delauney et al., 2010). Regardless, the recommendations are the same either for short or long-term deployments.

The recommendation includes the use of alternative technologies with minimal or no impact. For instance, ultrasonic, electrical and radiochemical technologies (Matsunaga et al., 1998), low frequency sound waves (Branscomb & Rittschof, 1984), and proteolytic enzymes inhibiting larval adhesion. Silicon technology is also a feasible alternative which could be easily removed by periodic cleaning operations (Terlizzi et al., 2000). The eco-friendly alternative for antifouling strategies can be divided into bionic and non-bionic. The bionic antifouling technologies mainly include simulated shark skin, whale skin, dolphin skin, coral tentacles, lotus leaves and other biological structures. In comparison, non-bionic antifouling technologies mainly include protein resistant polymers, antifoulant releasing coatings, foul release coatings, conductive antifouling coatings and photodynamic antifouling technology (Tian et al., 2021).

1.5. Non-Technical Summary

The development of a non-technical summary is required to compile information having regard, *inter alia*, to current knowledge and methods of assessment (Directive 2011/92/EU). With the objective to convey the key information in an understandable and concise manner, it should be a document that is appealing to read and easily understood by non-specialists (Eijssen & Jesus, 2015). In this context, an infographic (Figure 3) was developed compiling the most significant impacts when developing marine sensing technology. This infographic was shared with all partners to reduce the environmental impact of developing and demonstrating marine sensors and samplers.

Figure 3: Design of the non-technical summary for the environmental impact assessment for marine technologies.

2. DEMONSTRATIONS

During the demonstration phase, in which sensors are tested in the field for a certain period of time, there are preventive measures and guidelines to minimise the environmental impact and risk of accidents. These measures will be described in this section and are designed to ensure that professionals responsible for the operations assess and conduct the activities with the aim to prevent, mitigate and manage significant adverse impacts for the purpose of

preserving the marine environment. This includes planned activities that may have more than a minor or transitory effect on the marine environment or where the effects of the activity are unknown or poorly understood.

2.1. Loss of equipment

Introductory part of this section on the Deliverable 11.6 section 4.4. Complemented by the text below.

The recommendations vary depending on the plan for the deployment. In the case of the buoys, the primary measure to minimise the risk of failing to recover these sensors from the marine environment is to assess climate conditions and sea currents a priori and choose the best conditions for the deployments. In the context of the sensors attached to fishing gears, special attention was given to mount them properly and testing robustness to avoid loss due to shock while in use. Moreover, it is required for some sensors, for example, the lander and the AUV, that the recovery systems have a backup to retrieve the devices from the water if the primary recovery system fails.

For the sensors that are unmanned in the water column, it is recommended that all the sensors provide at least two strategies to recover the device from the marine environment. Note that, the development and adoption of this backup recovery system should not represent a higher environmental impact than if lost at sea. For instance, a combination of GPS and VHF systems was used to recover tags from pelagic sharks. Another example, it was added a second battery to recover the elephant seal tags, in case the first battery is exhausted.

In the case of an accidental loss, the sensor begins to corrode and sink to the seafloor where it will gradually disintegrate. During this process, the materials that compose the sensors and the respective accessories will be released in small amounts of pollutants into the ocean over a period of years. The chemical compounds leached into the seawater during this process are considered minimal and localised when compared to usual fluxes of these substances. The impact of corrosion and decomposition of a lost sensor is not expected to transcend local boundaries.

2.2. Ship Operations

For demonstration activities that require a research vessel, it is essential to follow the recommendations from the Code of Conduct for Marine Scientific Research Vessels International Ship Operators Meeting (Breslin, Nixon, & West, 2007), as well as the guidelines from the Marine Scientific Research section of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS, 2010). The aim is to minimise impacts while adopting a pragmatic approach that facilitates the conduct of marine scientific research. The main mitigation measure in these cases is to adopt a precautionary approach.

The code of conduct states that as part of a responsible research practice:

“Every vessel conducting marine science should develop a marine environmental management plan. The following are common areas where certain operations may have an impact and the complexity of these measures will vary on a case-by-case basis depending on such factors as vessel size, duration of voyage, geographical location, and mission type.”

These recommendations are particularly important in sensitive areas or areas already significantly impacted, where additional measures might be required. For instance, specialised training, equipment, crew, or procedures should be included in the management plan to minimise the impacts of the operation, such as anchoring, hazardous waste release, vessel noise emission, collision events, and others.

During the demonstrations within the project, the impact caused by boats is minimal due to the extensive experience of the crew and the vessels employed. The opportunistic use of fishing vessels or ferry boats is an alternative to reduce the need for vessels to acquire data. When these sensors reach the market, the boat impact should remain low if the proper protocols and good practices continue to be adopted.

2.3. Noise pollution

No sensors have indicated the release of acoustic energy at levels that would significantly affect local fauna. This impact is considered highly unlikely based on the activities projected within the scope of the project during the demonstration phase. It is possible that eventual encounters with cetaceans or other animals vulnerable to noise pollution occur during the project. However, no activity that could produce noise in a considerable high amplitude was identified to be considered a significant impact.

Noise pollution for marine mammals occurs mostly in the low frequency band (between 10Hz and 1 kHz). The use of research ships is necessary for some demonstrations, although normal vessel noise might not be so harmful to marine life, if not persistent or if the boat has a device to create significant noise (e.g. a strong sonar or seismic airguns). In the case of the active acoustic profiling sensor, it releases acoustic emissions usually as pulses from 300 kHz to 5 MHz at approximately 1 Watts, which is above the range typically used by marine mammals. More details on this topic are given in the Deliverable 3.6 section II.4., and also in the first version of the EIA, Deliverable 11.6 section 4.7.

2.4. Chemical Impacts

Given that some sensors and samplers might use potentially pollution chemical substances if it reaches seawater, either in the composition of the materials, equipment used during demonstration, or as a power source, the Article 194 from UNCLOS sets out the measures to be taken to prevent, reduce and control pollution from any source, including installations and devices operating in the marine environment. The most relevant to the latter are the measures designed to minimise to the fullest possible extent:

“(…) (b) pollution from vessels, in particular measures for preventing accidents and dealing with emergencies, ensuring the safety of operations at sea, preventing intentional and

unintentional discharges, and regulating the design, construction, equipment, operation and manning of vessels.

(...) (d) pollution from other installations and devices operating in the marine environment, in particular measures for preventing accidents and dealing with emergencies, ensuring the safety of operations at sea, and regulating the design, construction, equipment, operation and manning of such installations or devices.”

In addition, it also followed the statement in the section “Rights and obligations after the completion of the research” (UNCLOS, 2010) that it is the responsibility of the research institute to completely remove from the marine environment the scientific research installations or equipment after the research is completed.

As a mitigation measure to the eventual chemical impact caused by the sensors, such as dyes, copper and batteries, the Code of Conduct for Marine Scientific Research Vessels (ISOM, 2007) proposes that “the use of chemical tracers should be discouraged, as well as the use of expendable devices which contain hazardous materials. Where there is no alternative to these techniques, every effort should be taken to minimise their use.”

During the NAUTILOS project, several tests were carried out to ensure that no leakage of any kind occurred in the marine environment. By means of waterproof pressure housing, external batteries and other approaches to prevent chemical contamination, no expected toxic material should reach the marine environment under normal conditions. Complementarily, all the installations will be removed from the marine environment at the end of the project.

2.5. Autonomous Vehicles /Platforms

Some operations during the demonstrations will be carried out to integrate fixed and mobile platforms in coastal and shelf sea regions. Although this equipment is known for its low impact, there are some recommendations to be considered when conducting tests with the aerial, surface and underwater autonomous vehicles, as well as platforms and landers.

The environmental impact that these vehicles/structures may cause can be avoided if the necessary measures are taken in advance. The cruise plan should be designed to employ the most appropriate tool(s) to collect the scientific information while minimising the environmental impact, and the sampling methodologies should be designed to match the site-specific characteristics of the area, in particular through the use of less intrusive tools in sensitive and protected areas.

During lander operations, mooring deployments, remotely operated vehicle sampling, and other demonstration activities of this nature, special attention must be taken to avoid impacts that could be prevented. Such as unwanted chemical discharge (such as hydraulic fluid leakage), physical disturbance of delicate habitats caused by errors in manoeuvring and anchoring, pollution resulting from loss of equipment, and behavioural impact on marine life. This is why it was performed a careful risk assessment of the deployment plan before any equipment is tested during the project.

2.6. ARGO Floats

ARGO floats have an environmental impact associated with the decomposition of the old profiling floats in the seafloor after the usual three to six years of use. The floats that sank after their normal use, release toxic substances in the marine environment during the dismantling process of the materials that compose the profiling floats. Among the substances that are released by each dead float are around 0.1 kg of copper, 18 kg aluminium, 0.05 kg zinc, 2 kg plastic, 0.8 kg lead, and 0.2 kg of lithium. Some producers advocate that the amount of toxic substances is very small when compared to normal anthropogenic fluxes, and that the impact associated with the recovery of every float in the open ocean would be greater than just left the float to decompose in the ocean (Riser & Wijffels, 2020).

For the record, the project NAUTILOS does not foresee development of the ARGO float within the scope of the project. However, one sensor developed during the project will be demonstrated in these types of floats and will be recovered at the end of this activity.

3. IMPACTS AND MITIGATION MEASURES FROM SPECIFIC SENSORS AND ASSOCIATED DEPLOYMENTS

The impacts and mitigation measures for each sensor were assessed on a case-by-case basis. General information is compiled in the matrix of impacts (Table 3) and explained in detail for each sensor in the following sections. In addition, the respective demonstrations are also discussed in relation to the previously described impacts and mitigations.

3.1. Sensors and samplers

The compilation of the expected impacts of each sensor is displayed in the matrix of impacts (Table 3). The impacts are separated by phase (manufacturing, use and end of life), and divided into categories as discussed in the previous sections. The magnitude is illustrated by colours (see legend) and the sensors are listed on the y-axis of the matrix. After this concise display of the impacts, each sensor is discussed in detail, starting each section with a visual summary followed by discussing the respective individual impacts (when present) and mitigation measures.

Table 3: Matrix of impacts. The list of sensors, the identified impacts and respective magnitude.

	Manufacturing				Emissions	Use recovery rates	Facility of Repair	End of Life Recycling alternatives
	Pollutive materials	Source of Power	Antifouling	Sensitive areas				
Fluorometric DO Sensor	Green	Blue	Green	Green	Blue	Green	Green	Green
DO and Fluorescence Sensors	Green	Green	Green	Green	Blue	Green	Green	Green
IR sensor, LIDAR, Cameras (UAVs)	Green	Green	Blue	Blue	Blue	Green	Green	Green
Passive Acoustic sensor	Green	Green	Blue	Yellow	Blue	Green	Green	Green
Active Acoustic Profiling Sensor	Green	Green	Blue	Green	Blue	Green	Green	Green
Sampler for phytoplankton and other suspended matter	Green	Blue	Blue	Green	Blue	Green	Green	Green
Carbonate system/ocean acidification sensors	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
Silicate sensor	Green	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Green	Green
Submersible Nano- and Microplastics Sampler	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
Low-cost Microplastic sensors based on selective Nile Red staining	Green	Blue	Blue	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
Deep-ocean CTD	Green	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Green	Green	Green
Deep ocean low-level radioactivity sensor	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
Animal-borne tag (elasmobranchs)	Green	Green	Blue	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green
Animal-borne Instruments (elephant seals)	Green	Green	Blue	Red	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Green

Impact Magnitude

3.1.1. Fluorometric Sensors/Dissolved Oxygen

Fluorometric DO Sensor

Visual summary

Positive Impacts

- Dissolved Oxygen
- Ocean Color
- Plankton Biomass and diversity

Negative Impacts

No significant impact identified

Environmental Impact of the sensor

 Materials

 Power

 Antifouling

 Emissions

 Facility repair

 Recycling

No major concern is associated with this sensor. The entirely passive nature of this sampling technique, in addition to a deployment in a platform of opportunity, reduces the demand for infrastructure and environmental impact to acquire the data.

3.1.2. Dissolved Oxygen and Fluorescence Sensors

DO and Fluorescence Sensors

Visual summary

Positive Impacts

- Dissolved Oxygen
- Ocean Color
- Plankton Biomass and diversity

Negative Impacts

1. Lose the device

Mitigation

1. Robust sensor protection

Environmental Impact of the sensor

 Materials

 Power

 Antifouling

 Emissions

 Facility repair

 Recycling

The impact of these sensors is very low to insignificant if proper mitigation measures are taken, given the completely passive nature of the method used. The mitigation measures for the pair of sensors to be demonstrated on a bottom trawler in the Adriatic Sea include a robust protection to avoid damage and loss of the device. The possibility of losing the device is reduced by fixing the prototypes on the otter door with visible plastic protections, threaded steel bars, nuts and anti-shock rubber rings. This design is to avoid shocks and collisions with the seabed and other parts of the fishing gear.

The pair to be demonstrated on a fishing vessel in the Bay of Biscay will be deployed inside the pots used to catch crustaceans. This measure was taken to provide some degree of protection from other materials and minimise the risk of loss. The pair to be deployed in aquaculture plants in Brønnøysund, Norway will be recovered manually. Based on the passive nature of the sampling method, it does not represent any significant negative impact on the environment.

3.1.3. Downward-looking multi/hyperspectral and laser induced fluorescence sensors and cameras

Downward-looking multi/hyperspectral and laser induced fluorescence sensors and cameras

Visual summary

Positive Impacts

- Ocean Color
- Plankton Biomass and Diversity
- Sea surface Temperature

Negative Impacts

1. Lose the drone

Mitigation

1. Robust sensor protection

Environmental Impact of the sensor

Materials	Power	Antifouling	Emissions	Facility repair	Recycling

No major concern is associated with this sensor. This is because they remotely collect data, in a passive and non-invasive way. For the hyperspectral sensor mounted in a drone, no impact is expected since it will be carried out by an experienced drone pilot. Although it produces noise, it is not in an amplitude high enough to represent a threat to the native fauna.

For the sensors deployed in the Ferrybox, the impacts are negligible due to the remote nature of the sampling method, the low chances of losing the device and the use of an opportunistic observation platform, reducing the need for infrastructure, thus reducing the impact associated with the operation of this device.

3.1.4. Passive broadband acoustic recording sensor for noise monitoring / Passive acoustic event recorder / Active Acoustic Profiling Sensor

Active Acoustic Profiling Sensor / Passive Acoustic sensor

Visual summary

Positive Impacts

- Marine mammals abundance and distribution
- Ocean Sound

Negative Impacts

1. Lose the lander

Mitigation

1. Backup recovery system
2. Follow appropriate protocols during demonstrations in MPAs

Environmental Impact of the sensor

Materials	Power	Antifouling	Emissions	Facility repair	Recycling

These sensors use non-destructive techniques to collect data about cetaceans' presence and abundance by the means of hydrophones. During the time the sensors are deployed in seawater it produces no significant impact, since they rely on harmless approaches to collect data. The deployments of the passive sensors are predicted to be in a marine area with high abundance of cetaceans. It requires some precautionary approach, with a group of cetaceans that are sighted nearby; however, if these protocols of approach are followed, no greater impact is expected. It is worth mentioning that no direct interaction with populations of dolphins and whales in the natural environment is predicted in this project, only deployment of the acoustic sensors to record their vocalization.

Given the different strategies to deploy the acoustic recorders, the impact associated to the deployment is slightly different. The passive acoustic recorder deployed in aquaculture and fishing boats (see section IV.3.2.1) has a lower chance of losing the device than the acoustic recorder which will be installed in the lander. Nevertheless, as mentioned before, the probability of failing to recover these platforms is very low given the extensive experience of the professionals involved in these activities.

Regarding the active acoustic profiling sensor, it will be integrated within the lander with other sensors. In fact, the device functions as an active sonar, though it has a limited range and typically operates at frequencies higher than those used by marine mammals (over 200 kHz). Additionally, its operating duty cycle will be relatively low due to the battery autonomy, this short deployment period reduces the probability of an eventual impact. To reduce the risk of disturbing marine animals, the transmitted sound pressure levels can be minimized by enhancing the receiver's sensitivity.

In addition, a mitigation measure for products and accessories, including batteries, is that the company will offer free recycling for all electronic equipment at the end of its life. Once the product is returned to the designated collection point.

3.1.5. Sampler for phytoplankton and other suspended matter

Sampler for phytoplankton and other suspended matter

Visual summary

Positive Impacts

- Suspended particles
- Plankton Biomass and diversity
- Stable carbon isotopes

Negative Impacts

No significant impact identified

Environmental Impact of the sensor

Materials

Power

Antifouling

Emissions

Facility repair

Recycling

No major concern associated with this sensor. It uses a ferryboat as a platform of opportunity, which considerably reduces the impact associated with this sensor.

3.1.6. Carbonate system/ocean acidification sensors

Carbonate system/ocean acidification sensors

Visual summary

Positive Impacts

- Suspended particles
- Plankton Biomass and diversity
- Stable carbon isotopes

Negative Impacts

No significant impact identified

Environmental Impact of the sensor

Materials

Power

Antifouling

Emissions

Facility repair

Recycling

There is no major concern associated with this sensor. It uses a ferryboat as a platform of opportunity, which considerably reduces the impact associated with this sensor.

3.1.7. Silicate Electrochemical Sensor

NKE Silicate sensor

Visual summary

Positive Impacts

- Inorganic Macronutrient

Negative Impacts

1. Do not recover the device
2. Marine pollution due to lost device

Mitigation

1. Knowledge of the currents in the deployment zone and estimate the drift according to the seawater currents
2. Choose less pollutant materials (biodegradable)

Environmental Impact of the sensor

Materials	Power	Antifouling	Emissions	Facility repair	Recycling

The impact caused by the silicate sensor in the marine environment is low with regard to the sampling techniques under normal use. The discharge of the silicate molybdate complex in these amounts does not represent a threat to marine life, nor a change the pH of the seawater at local level.

During the activities predicted within the project, the sensors will be demonstrated in 3-4 days missions and then recovered for evaluation. However, in future deployments of the ARGO floats, these sensors might be not recovered; thus, subjected to decomposing in the marine environment. This issue is addressed in the section 2.6 ARGO Floats.

3.1.8. Submersible Nano- and Microplastics Sampler - Submersible Sampler for Nanoplastics and Microplastics (SCT)

Submersible Nano- and Microplastics Sampler

Visual summary

Positive Impacts

- Litter including microplastic

Negative Impacts

1. Failing of acoustic releaser leading to no recovery

Mitigation

1. Backup system for recovering

Environmental Impact of the sensor

Materials

Power

Antifouling

Emissions

Facility repair

Recycling

No major concern is associated with this sensor. It does not rely on chemical separation of the plastic particles. The failure of the acoustic releaser can happen although very unlikely which would result in no recovery and dismantling of the sensor in the marine environment. For this purpose, a backup system for recovering these sensors is being developed.

3.1.9. Low-cost Microplastic sensors based on selective Nile Red staining and fluorescence detection

Low-cost Microplastic sensors based on selective Nile Red staining and fluorescence detection

Visual summary

Positive Impacts

- Litter including microplastics

Negative Impacts

1. Possible contaminations of seawater with reagents

Mitigation

1. Collection of all the reagents and proper disposal

Environmental Impact of the sensor

Materials

Power

Antifouling

Emissions

Facility repair

Recycling

In contrast to the other microplastic sensor, this device relies on the chemical affinity of the plastic particles to dye and sort out the pieces for quantification. The by-products of these processes are potassium hydroxide (KOH) and the Nile Red (fluorescent staining agent) that will be collected as wastewater and disposed of professionally.

3.1.10. Deep Ocean CTD

Deep-ocean CTD

Visual summary

Positive Impacts

- Sea surface temperature and salinity
- Subsurface temperature and salinity

Negative Impacts

1. Corrosion by seawater
2. Float collision and loss

Mitigation

1. Knowledge of sea currents and chose appropriate weather conditions for demonstration

Environmental Impact of the sensor

Materials	Power	Antifouling	Emissions	Facility repair	Recycling

The CTD for deep waters also has very low impact (such as most CTDs). Although some degree of corrosion on the housing has been observed, the amount of material released to the marine environment is insignificant. There is a risk of losing the sensor given the depth it will be deployed; however, this risk is low if standard procedures are adopted.

3.1.11. Deep ocean low-level radioactivity sensor

UL-FE Deep-ocean CTD

Visual summary

Positive Impacts

- Radioactivity

Negative Impacts

1. Leakage due to excessive pressure in the system

Mitigation

1. The battery unit remains separated from the sensor.

Environmental Impact of the sensor

Materials	Power	Antifouling	Emissions	Facility repair	Recycling

The subsea radioactivity sensor has an impact of very low magnitude. The radioactivity receptor is totally passive, not emitting any kind of radioactivity emitters in the marine environment. The battery is placed in a chamber with oil, due to the high pressures, which has been tested to guarantee it does not leak. No toxic material has been reported for this sensor.

3.1.12. Animal-borne sensor (sharks and rays)

Animal-borne tag (elasmobranchs)

Visual summary

Positive Impacts

- Dissolved Oxygen
- Fish abundance & distribution

Negative Impacts

1. Disturbing the animals
2. Drag
3. Lead in the weight
4. Coloration

Mitigation

1. Non-invasive method, use of a trained and experienced crew
2. Calculated empirically the drag for the target species
3. Use stainless steel or basalt as alternative
4. Short-duration deployment (>72 hours)

Environmental Impact of the sensor

 Materials

 Power

 Antifouling

 Emissions

 Facility repair

 Recycling

This novel tag to track elasmobranchs has some of the lowest levels of impact for this class of devices. The non-invasive animal towed tagging system results in little or neglectable immediate changes in behaviour for the animals (Fontes et al., 2018), which can be observed in the post-tagging descending rates and tail beat frequency as a proxies of stress caused by the attachment of the device (Gleiss et al., 2009; Saraiva et al., 2023). When towed tags are deployed non-invasively on free swimming sharks and mobulas, the animals were observed to return to their normal swimming pattern within a few minutes after tagged, showing the low direct impact in the behaviour of these animals. When sharks had to be retained for tagging, the recovery period was approximately 30 min. After this short recovery period, the sharks displayed regular behaviour (descent rates and tail beat frequency) (Saraiva et al., 2023).

To assess the potential impacts in animal-borne tags they were divided into four categories and presented in Table 4 adapted from McMahon et al. (2011).

Table 4: Potential impacts of animal-borne sensors (adapted from McMahon et al., 2011).

Stages of device deployment	Points to consider
Capture	selection capture restrain release extreme stress levels
Device type	size and shape positioning drag colour
Attachment method	potential to harm impairment of movement feather loss necrosis under the unit
Timing and attachment duration	biology larger duration may exacerbate the effects

There are three target species to be instrumented within the scope of the project, these are sicklefin devil rays (*Mobula tarapacana*), blunt nose sixgill sharks (*Hexanchus griseus*), and blue sharks (*Prionace glauca*).

The tagging procedure for manta rays and blue sharks is done usually in free-swimming individuals that are attracted using “chumming” while experienced free-divers place adjustable harness between the head and the pectoral fins of the animals (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Tagging procedure for blue shark (left) and sicklefin devil ray with a harness (right).

In contrast, the blunt nose sixgill shark has to be captured since it is a deep-water shark. Therefore, it has to be fished using large circle hooks to prevent deep hooking injuring the guts and gills, and to allow quick release after tagging with tow attachment with harness, so intramuscular anchors will not be used. They will be fished at night, when the animals migrate

to the shallow habitat, at around 200 m and brought slowly to the surface (around 40-60 minutes). The animal is turned to an upside-down position, to induce tonic immobility (Figure 5) and the tagging procedure is swift (2 minutes). The animals are released immediately after. This procedure causes minimal changes in behaviour within the first 12 hours after release and no mortality was ever observed. Only wild animals are used in the demonstrations which will not be kept in captivity or scientific facilities.

Figure 5: Tagging procedure for sixgill sharks, placing them into a natural tonic immobility position.

The torpedo shape of the device reduces its drag and flow through the water column without adding significant drag to the animals. The evaluation on the site regarding the animals able to be instrumented is carried out by specialists, taking into consideration size, age, physical conditions, and other biological factors. The increment in the drag of these individuals caused by this model of tag has been empirically tested (Fontes et al., 2022). The increase in the ratio of the tag to animal drag was evaluated, establishing a threshold for size of individuals that can be tagged. It was concluded that the energetic costs of carrying this device for rays larger than 3 metres and blue sharks larger than 2.5 metres are lower than a 5% drag increase, acceptable for short-term deployments (12-48 hours) which is the average duration of the demonstrations conducted during this project for this tag.

The impact caused by the red coloration on the tagged individuals related to food acquisition and predation (Wilson & McMahon, 2006) is not of major concern due to the short-term deployment of these tags and because red colour radiation is absorbed in the first metres of the water column, thus becoming difficult to detect for most animals. In addition, the red coloration makes it easier to sight the sensor in the open ocean and maintain the recovery rates at 100%, as reported for this sensor.

No highly toxic material was reported for this animal-borne tag. The external part is made of synthetic foam and micro-spheres, the internal devices are made of titanium and epoxy resin

among other materials. The repair is facilitated, and the sensor can be recharged and used multiple times, the basic maintenance includes changing the O₂ sensor membrane after a certain number of deployments.

Although this sensor is required to handle the wild animals and has some degree of impact, it has the lowest magnitude of impact for sensors that acquire this type of data. The levels of impact for this sensor are within the acceptable levels, when the mitigation measures are followed, giving the benefits of the value of the information they collect.

3.1.13. Animal-borne tag (elephant seals)

Animal-borne tag (elephant seals)

Visual summary

Positive Impacts

- Dissolved Oxygen
- Ocean Color

Negative Impacts

1. Anaesthesia procedure
2. Lost in the marine environment

Mitigation

1. Trained and experienced crew, follow ethical protocols
2. Backup recovery system

Environmental Impact of the sensor

Materials	Power	Antifouling	Emissions	Facility repair	Recycling

The impacts of the new sensor for pinnipeds are addressed in this section, with emphasis on the mitigation measures reported by the researchers conducting the demonstrations. Following the same rationale, to evaluate the impact of this animal-borne tag the same criteria presented in Table 4 will be used regarding animal-borne tracking devices.

To capture the animal, the protocols to attach the devices in elephant seals are well developed and extensively tested. The appropriate amount of anaesthesia determined for each size class of animals is administered intravenously. The drug Zoletil has been widely used to induce anaesthesia in these animals (Field et al., 2002), it has been observed to be very effective for elephant seals, in contrast to fur seals, being the best choice for the purpose of this demonstration. In the project, only large females after the lactating period will be tagged. The authorisation was provided by the French Polar Environment Committee. The handling and anaesthesia procedures within the scope of this project was approved by the French (cf. APAFIS N°19-040 #21375 delivered on the 13/07/2019) and Argentinian Ethics Committees and animal handling and experimentation.

Another very effective approach to attach these devices is using gas anaesthesia, providing more safety to both the animal and the researchers handling the animal. Nevertheless, the

equipment with the gas anaesthesia weighs around 25 kg, which makes it hard to access in remote areas.

After the animal is stabilised, a small platform is glued to the head or back fur using a two-component fast setting araldite (Figure 6). The sensor is fixed into this platform to facilitate the recovery process. One precaution during this process is to avoid excessive heat released during the exothermic reaction from the glue. Regarding the excess of heat, it is critical to respect the good proportion of hardener and resin, for that a mixing tube has been used on a double compartment syringe. Araldite exothermic reactions tend to be lighter than the epoxy one and as such should be preferred over epoxy (who tend to be too brittle). Since the weight of the tag is around 0.26% of the total departure weight of an adult female elephant seal, it is expected that this tag does not negatively affect the mass gain and survival of these large marine mammals during the time they are being tracked (McMahon et al., 2008).

The recovery process consists of tracking the position of the tagged animal, immobilising it and cutting the attachment that connects the sensor to the platform. Recovery rates around 80-90% have been reported, due i) to normal mortality of this species (normal death rate around 5%) and ii) to the animals being in inaccessible areas, making the operation risky for the professionals involved. To increase the success of the recovery rates of these tags, another independent battery was included to power a backup Argos satellite system. This is to guarantee that the position of the tag will be transmitted regardless if the system used for data collection runs out of battery. This means that if only one of the Argos tags is still transmitting, the other one is out-of-order, if both Argos tags stop transmitting simultaneously it means that the animal is dead. Dead seals float belly up, before sinking after being scavenged by seabirds. Argos tags do not transmit as long as they are underwater.

In case the sensor is not recovered, it will be lost in the ocean or on land during the next moult (the annual renewal of the fur). As everything is strongly cast in epoxy no leaking of lithium in the environment is expected. For the recovered sensors, they are brought to the research facilities, the full data set archived on-board the tag is downloaded, and the battery must be replaced for the next deployment. The process of changing the battery is not trivial, since the sensor needs a robust cover given the pressure it must support during the extreme deep dives of these animals (up to 2000 metres).

Figure 6: An elephant seal successfully instrumented.

3.2. Deployments

Many demonstration activities will be conducted in sites already subjected to long-term scientific research. Some of these activities have a very low impact while others require the adoption of the precautionary approach described in the next sections of this document. The demonstrations predicted in the scope of the project are listed and the relative impact discussed.

3.2.1. Demonstrations on Fisheries and Aquaculture Observing Systems

The fisheries and aquaculture observing systems will be installed in some vessels and aquaculture plants in European waters. The impact of these demonstration activities has very low magnitude, since these sensors will be deployed in boats of opportunity and aquaculture sites that are already in activity, with the added impact from NAUTILOS activities considered irrelevant.

The acoustic marine mammal monitoring system is a passive sampler, therefore causing almost no negative impact while in use. This sensor will be deployed in two different locations: i) the Swedish Sound/Kullaberg/Lysekil waters in the Kattegat and Skagerrak areas of the North Sea, between the west coast of Sweden and the east coast of Denmark, ii) the Portofino Marine Protected Area (MPA) or other area with abundance of cetaceans. The first region is known for its diverse marine ecosystem, including a wide range of fish species and marine mammals. The water depth ranges from 10 to 200 meters, with some areas close to shore having a depth of only a few meters. The commercial fishermen will deploy the AQUAclick Sound from their fishing vessels, which will serve as a platform for the deployment. The second area is located off the coast of Italy and is a protected marine area designated for the conservation of cetaceans. The demonstration will be carried out by partner institutions,

who will deploy the AQUAclick Sound attaching it to a fixed oceanographic point. The missions to deploy this sensor should cause no greater concern if the recommendations described in the section 2.2 Ship Operations from this document are followed.

3.2.2. Demonstration on platforms of opportunity

The operational use of the platform of opportunity will be demonstrated in Ferrybox infrastructures in the following locations: Coastal Norway; Gulf of Finland; and Eastern Mediterranean (Cretan Sea). These demonstrations will include the following sensors: Downward-looking multi/hyperspectral and laser induced fluorescence sensors. Sampler for phytoplankton and other suspended matter. Carbonate system/ocean acidification sensors. Low-cost microplastic sensors based on selective Nile Red staining and fluorescence detection.

Given the opportunistic nature of this demonstration activity, the added impact of these sensors on the impact already created by these large vessels is insignificant. Regarding the development phase, the impacts and respective mitigation measures are described in the next sections.

3.2.3. Demonstrations on Augmented Observing Systems

In this demonstration, some activities are predicted to deploy the recently developed sensors in different fixed-point observatories. For most of these activities, it will be necessary a research vessel, which the good practices to avoid environmental impacts are addressed in section 2.2 Ship Operations. During these activities, special attention is given to the mooring sites, aiming to avoid mooring the platforms in delicate environmental habitats. Since most of these platforms such as the profiling buoy and the lander are deployed in deep waters (>100 m depth), it is difficult to predict the environmental impact underneath. Nevertheless, these platforms should not release any contaminants into the water.

A more detailed explanation of the disturbance possibly caused by these autonomous vehicles and platforms is given in section 2.5 Autonomous Vehicles /Platforms and in section 2.4 Chemical Impacts.

Given the depth where these demonstrations will take place, there is the chance (although remote) to fail to recover the sensors. These activities will be carried out by experienced professionals from the partner institutes that are used to carry out deployments of this nature, reducing the chances of an accidental loss to occur. Anyways, recommendations are given in section 2.1 Loss of equipment.

3.2.4. Demonstration on ARGO platform

This task consists of implementing a new generation of silicate sensors onto an ARGO profiling float. Although ARGO floats have well known environmental impacts (Riser & Wijffels, 2020), and have been collecting large amounts of data in remote locations crucial for ocean observing systems, they are often not recovered from the marine environment and decompose on the seafloor. These impacts, although negative, allow us to collect data from many locations simultaneously and continuously in inaccessible areas of the ocean.

Among the substances released into the seawater where the buoys decompose are copper, aluminium, lithium from the batteries, plastic, and usually an antifouling substance. It has been argued that the impact caused by the quantity of toxic substances that might spill during the degrading process is negligible when compared to natural and anthropogenic fluxes (Riser & Wijffels, 2020). It is advocated that the impact of recovering every buoy would be greater than leaving them in the marine environment, also that the great distance between buoys attenuates the impact caused individually by these devices, and this is the best method so far to collect data of this nature and frequency.

Nevertheless, in the NAUTILOS project, a single demonstration event for the silicate sensor is expected to be carried out, being deployed in an ARGO profiling float. The location where this activity will take place is in the Mediterranean Sea (likely towards the eastern portion) where the depth reaches 2000 meters. The deployment is expected to take 3-4 days and the Argo float will be recovered at the end of that mission. More detail is provided about the ARGO float in section 2.6 ARGO Floats.

3.2.5. Animal-borne instruments

The demonstration of the two animal-borne sensors developed during the project will be carried out in the Azores, Portugal and in either the Valdes Peninsula, Argentina or in the Kerguelen Island in the southern Indian Ocean. All three sites are considered pristine with rich marine life. The impact and mitigation measures associated with these sensors are addressed in sections 3.1.12 Animal-borne sensor (sharks and rays) 3.1.13 Animal-borne sensor (elephant seal), respectively. The selection of the site for the demonstration takes into account areas where these species are present and accessible. As well as, if the area is not subject to a current impact where the added impact from NAUTILOS activity could represent a significant cumulative impact on the wild populations of these species, such as in the case of changing the location from the Valdez Peninsula due to an epidemic where the death rates increased dramatically on elephant seals.

V. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

After a thorough analysis of the possible impacts originated from the project, it is concluded that the significant impacts have a relatively low magnitude, with no greater concerns when the mitigation measures are followed. Through the course of the project, it has been extensively assessed the development and demonstration of these recently developed marine technologies. This new generation of sensors, samplers and respective platforms have remarkably low impact with the adoption of passive or non-destructive sampling techniques.

The operation of these new technologies requires some procedures to not impact the marine environment negatively. However, when these measures and good practices are adopted very low impact is expected from the development, deployment, and data collection. When the positive impacts the project has on the marine environment are considered, a definitely positive outcome is expected from all the activities developed within the scope of the project NAUTILOS. Nevertheless, this needs to be confirmed when the sensors will be deployed in the demonstration areas followed by monitoring of possible effects in the marine environment.

VI. APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

ID	Reference or Related Document	Source or Link/Location
1	Branscomb, E. S., & Rittschof, D. (1984). An investigation of low frequency sound waves as a means of inhibiting barnacle settlement. <i>Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology</i> , 79(2), 149–154.	https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-0981(84)90215-6
2	Breslin, J., Nixon, D., & West, G. (2007). <i>Code of conduct for marine scientific research vessels</i> . International Ship Operators Meeting (ISOM). Qingdao, China, 17-20 October 2007.	https://www.irso.info/wp-content/uploads/International_RV_Code_final.pdf
3	Delauney, L., Compere, C., & Lehaitre, M. (2010). Biofouling protection for marine environmental sensors. <i>Ocean Science</i> , 6(2), 503-511.	https://doi.org/10.5194/os-6-503-2010
4	Deliverable11.6_NAUTILOS_v4_final_version.docx	Deliverable 11.6 – Environmental Impact Assessment – first version
5	Directive 2014/52/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 April 2014 amending Directive 2011/92/EU on the assessment of the effects of certain public and private projects on the environment. <i>Official Journal of the European Union</i> .	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32014L0052
6	Directive 2011/65/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 8 June 2011 on the restriction of the use of certain hazardous substances in electrical and electronic equipment Text with EEA relevance. <i>Official Journal of the European Union</i> .	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32011L0065
7	Eijssen, P., & Jesus, J. (2015). Non-Technical Summary. International Association for Impact Assessment. 23rd Street South, Suite C Fargo, ND 58103-3705 USA.	https://www.iaia.org/pdf/Fastips_9%20NonTechnical%20Summary.pdf
8	EU European Commission. (2021). <i>35 years of EU Environmental Impact Assessment</i> . Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.	https://environnement.public.lu/content/dam/environnement/documents/emweltprozeduren/eie/eie-infobox/EIA-Directive-35-years.pdf

9	Field, I. C., Bradshaw, C. J. A., McMahon, C. R., Harrington, J., & Burton, H. R. (2002). Effects of age, size and condition of elephant seals (<i>Mirounga leonina</i>) on their intravenous anaesthesia with tiletamine and zolazepam. <i>Veterinary Record</i> , 151(8), 235–240.	https://doi.org/10.1136/vr.151.8.235
10	Fontes, J., Baeyaert, J., Prieto, R., Graça, G., Buyle, F., & Afonso, P. (2018). New non-invasive methods for short-term electronic tagging of pelagic sharks and rays. <i>Marine Biology</i> , 165(2), 1–13.	https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-018-3289-z
11	Fontes, J., Macena, B., Solleliet-Ferreira, S., Buyle, F., Magalhães, R., Bartolomeu, T., Liebsch, N., Meyer, C., & Afonso, P. (2022). The advantages and challenges of non-invasive towed PILOT tags for free-ranging deep-diving megafauna. <i>Animal Biotelemetry</i> , 10(1), 1–13.	https://doi.org/10.1186/s40317-022-00310-1
12	Glasson, J., & Therivel, R. (2013). <i>Introduction to environmental impact assessment</i> . Routledge.	https://www.routledge.com/Introduction-To-Environmental-Impact-Assessment/Glasson-Therivel/p/book/9781138600751
13	Gleiss, A. C., Norman, B., Liebsch, N., Francis, C., & Wilson, R. P. (2009). A new prospect for tagging large free-swimming sharks with motion-sensitive data-loggers. <i>Fisheries Research</i> , 97(1–2), 11–16.	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2008.12.012
14	Matsunaga, T., Nakayama, T., Wake, H., Takahashi, M., Okochi, M., & Nakamura, N. (1998). Prevention of marine biofouling using a conductive paint electrode. <i>Biotechnology and Bioengineering</i> , 59(3), 374–378.	<a href="https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-0290(19980805)59:3<374::AID-BIT14>3.0.CO;2-E">https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-0290(19980805)59:3<374::AID-BIT14>3.0.CO;2-E
15	McMahon, C. R., Collier, N., Northfield, J. K., & Glen, F. (2011). Taking the time to assess the effects of remote sensing and tracking devices on animals. <i>Animal Welfare</i> , 20(4), 515–521.	https://doi.org/10.1017/S0962728600003158
16	McMahon, C. R., Field, I. C., Bradshaw, C. J. A., White, G. C., & Hindell, M. A. (2008). Tracking and data-logging devices attached to elephant seals do not affect individual mass gain or survival. <i>Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology</i> , 360(2), 71–77.	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jembe.2008.03.012

17	Morgan, R. K. (1999). <i>Environmental impact assessment: A methodological approach</i> . Springer Science & Business Media.	https://link.springer.com/book/9780412729904
18	Riser, S. C., & Wijffels, S. (2020). Environmental issues and the Argo array. SOCCOM.	https://www.argo.org.cn/uploadfile/file/20210805/final.Argo_Environmental_Impact.2020.05.10-1.pdf
19	Saraiva, B. M., Macena, B. C., Solleliet-Ferreira, S., Afonso, P., & Fontes, J. (2023). First insights into the shortfin mako shark (<i>Isurus oxyrinchus</i>) fine-scale swimming behaviour. <i>Royal Society Open Science</i> , 10(5), 230012.	https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.230012
20	Terlizzi, A., Conte, E., Zupo, V., & Mazzella, L. (2000). Biological succession on silicone fouling-release surfaces: Long-term exposure tests in the Harbour of Ischia, Italy. <i>Biofouling</i> , 15(4), 327–342.	https://doi.org/10.1080/08927010009386322
21	Tian, L., Yin, Y., Bing, W., & Jin, E. (2021). Antifouling technology trends in marine environmental protection. <i>Journal of Bionic Engineering</i> , 18(2), 239–263.	https://doi.org/10.1007/s42235-021-0017-z
22	United Nations. (2010). <i>The law of the sea: Marine scientific research: A revised guide to the implementation of the relevant provisions of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea</i> . United Nations Division for Ocean Affairs and the Law of the Sea, Office of Legal Affairs. 88 pp.	http://dx.doi.org/10.25607/OBP-479
23	Wilson, R. P., & McMahon, C. R. (2006). Measuring devices on wild animals: What constitutes acceptable practice? <i>Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment</i> , 4(3), 147–154.	https://doi.org/10.1890/1540-9295(2006)004[0147:MDOWAW]2.0.CO;2